

БИМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

9 ЖИЛД, 4 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 9, НОМЕР 4

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 4

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MORPHOLOGY AND MORPHOMETRIC CHARACTERISTICS OF LIVER TISSUE OF GROUP FIFTH WHITE RATS

For citation: Usanov S. Sanjar, Abduraimov A. Zafarjan. Morphology and morphometric characteristics of liver tissue of group fifth white rats. // Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. 2024, vol. 9, issue 4, pp.305-311

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13710151>

ANNOTATION

A particularly important place in the relationship of the whole organism with the external environment is occupied by the digestive system. The liver, as the main excretory organ, is highly susceptible to the negative effects of medicines. Anti-inflammatory drugs are one of the most commonly used medicinal groups in medicine. Their advantage is a complex effect (antipyretic, anti-inflammatory and analgesic), as well as a wide range of indications for which they can be used. 5 types of anti-inflammatory drugs are more common and often prescribed, which are included in the same group according to pharmacodynamic effects. However, the information available today on the results of therapy with these drugs does not allow us to draw an unambiguous conclusion about their effectiveness or inefficiency, as well as about the development of side effects in such combinations.

Key words: liver, parenchimy, central vena, biliary duct, polypharmacy.

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МОРФОЛОГИЯ И МОРФОМЕТРИЧЕСКАЯ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА ТКАНИ ПЕЧЕНИ БЕЛЫХ КРЫС ПЯТОЙ ГРУППЫ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Особо важное место во взаимоотношении всего организма с внешней средой занимает пищеварительная система. Печень, как главный экскреторный орган, в большой степени подвержены негативному воздействию лекарственных средств. Противовоспалительные средства это одна из наиболее часто используемых в медицине лекарственных групп. Их преимуществом является комплексное действие (жаропонижающее, противовоспалительное

и обезболивающее), а также широкий спектр показаний, при которых они могут использоваться. Более распространены и часто назначаются 5 видов противовоспалительных средств, входящие в одну группу по фармакодинамическим эффектам. Однако имеющиеся на сегодня сведения о результатах терапии данными препаратами не позволяют сделать однозначный вывод об их эффективности или неэффективности а так же о развитие побочных эффектов в таких комбинациях.

Ключевые слова: печень, паренхима, центральная вена, желчные протоки, полипрагмазия.

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BESHINCHI GURUHDAGI OQ KALAMUSHLAR JIGARI TO'QIMASINING MORFOLOGIYASI VA MORFOMETRIK TAVSIFI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ovqat hazm qilish tizimi butun organizmning tashqi muhit bilan munosabatlarida ayniqsa muhim o'rin tutadi. Jigar, asosiy ekskretator organ sifatida, dori vositalarining salbiy ta'siriga juda moyil. Yallig'lanishga qarshi dorilar bu tibbiyotda eng ko'p ishlatiladigan dorilar guruhlaridan biridir. Ularning afzalligi murakkab ta'sir (antipiretik, yallig'lanishga qarshi va og'riq qoldiruvchi) va ulardan foydalanish mumkin bo'lgan keng ko'lamli ko'rsatkichlardir. Farmakodinamik ta'sirlar bo'yicha bir guruhga kiritilgan yallig'lanishga qarshi dorilarning 5 turi ko'proq tarqalgan va ko'pincha buyuriladi. Biroq, bugungi kunda ushbu dorilar bilan terapiya natijalari to'g'risidagi ma'lumotlar ularning samaradorligi yoki samarasizligi, shuningdek, bunday kombinatsiyalarda yon ta'sirlarning rivojlanishi to'g'risida aniq xulosa chiqarishga imkon bermaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: jigar, parenxima, markaziy vena, o't yo'llari, polipragmaziya.

DOLZARBLIGI. Hozirgi vaqtda jigarda patologik jarayonlarni o'rganishga tavsiflovchi yondashuv yetarli emas. Organ va to'qimalarda o'zgarishlarni aniq va ob'ektiv baholash uchun mikropreparatlar, xususan, morfometrik, tadqiqot usullari va olingan ma'lumotlarning statistik tahlilini keng qo'llash kerak, bu nafaqat o'rganilayotgan hodisalarning xarakterini va tavsifini baholashning aniqligini oshiribgina qolmay, balki morfologik tashxisni kerak

Jigar ovqat hazm qilish tizimining patologiyasi inson kasallanishi va o'lim holatlarining strukturasi yetakchi o'rinlardan birini egallaydi.

Jigar shikastlanishi nafaqat viruslar yoki gepatotropik toksinlar, balki ko'plab preparatlar bilan ham bog'liq bo'lishi mumkin. Odatda, bu dori vositalariga nisbatan yuqori sezuvchanlikka ega bo'lgan va insonning individual genetik xususiyatlariga bog'liq bo'lgan shaxslarda sodir bo'ladi. O'tkir shikastlanish organ parenximasida gepatotsitlarga sitotoksik yoki sitolitik ta'sir tufayli, safro chiqarish tizimining elementlarida (xolestatik shikastlanishlar) yoki kombinatsiyalangan bo'lishi mumkin. Turli ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, klinik jihatdan aniqlangan sariqlik holatlarining 5% dan ortig'i dori vositalariga qabul qilish bilan bog'liq. Shu bilan birga, 10% hollarda noma'lum etiologiyaning surunkali gepatit bilan og'rigan bemorlarni tekshirishda laboratoriya parametrlarining o'zgarishi dori vositalariga qabul qilish bilan bog'liq bo'lishi mumkin

Taxminan 90% hollarda virusli gepatit o'tkir boshlanadi.

Ushbu muhim organning patologiyasi va uning terapiyasi masalalarini o'rganishda laboratoriya va qishloq xo'jalik hayvonlarida keng qamrovli tadqiqotlar o'tkazish oqlanadi, chunki bu laboratoriya sharoitida eksperimentdan ko'ra ko'proq inson va hayvon kasalliklarida dori vositalarining ta'sirini baholashdan iborat

Statistik ma'lumotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, yallig'lanishga qarshi dori vositalari polipragmaziya tez-tez uchraydi va har qanday mutaxassis shifokor ham bunga yo'l qo'yishi mumkin. Bunga COVID-19 pandemiyasi davrida ayniqsa ko'prok yo'l qo'yilgan.

MAQSAD VA VAZIFALAR: Polipragmaziyada yallig'lanishga qarshi dori vositalari (paratsetamol, aspirin, ibuprofen, deksametazon, gidroksixloroxin sulfat) ta'sirida besh oylik bo'lgan oq zotsiz kalamush jigar parenximasidagi morfologik o'zgarishlarning xususiyatlarini aniqlash va baholashdan iborat bo'lgan.

MATERIAL VA USULLAR. Jigar to'qimasining umumiy makropreparati va eksperimental kalamushlar jigar to'qimasining turli qismlaridan olingan gistologik materiallar xizmat qilgan.

Qo'yilgan vazifalarni hal etish uchun eksperimental, morfologik, morfometrik va statistik tadqiqot usullaridan foydalanilgan.

NATIJA VA XULOSALAR: Tadqiqotning beshinchi guruhidan maksadi oq zotsiz kalamushlarga besh xildagi yallig'lanishga qarshi dorilarni kiritish yo'li bilan jigar parenximasi tizimidagi morfometrik o'zgarishlarni o'rganish.

Beshinchi guruhga tajriba uchun eksperiment (n=50) oq zotsiz kalamushlar olindi. Beshinchi guruh ok zotsiz kalamushlarga rivojlanishning 141 kundan boshlab 150 kunigacha 10 kun mobaynida metal zond orkali oshkozon ichiga yallig'lanishga qarshi 5 xil paratsetamol 15 mg/kg, aspirin 5 mg/kg, ibuprofen 6 mg/kg, deksametazon 0,1 mg/k gidroksixloroxin sulfat 6,5 mg/kg g dori vositalari yuborildi;

Ushbu dori dozalari empirik tarzda hisoblab chiqilgan va har kun oshqozon ichiga 10 kun davomida eritma shaklida qo'llanilgan.

Beshinchi eksperiment guruhi ok zotsiz kalamushlarining vazni 182.1g dan 228.7 g gacha, o'rtacha 205.8 g gacha bo'ldi. Kalamushlarning beshinchi eksperiment guruhi jigar massasi 6.95 g dan 8.96 g gacha, o'rtacha – 7.77 ± 0.24 g gacha.

Oq zotsiz kalamushning jigar uzunligi beshinchi eksperiment guruhda 2,6 dan 3,4sm, o'rtacha uzunligi $2,95 \pm 0,09$ sm ni tashkil etadi.

Ok kalamush jigarining yuqori va pastki qirg'oqlar orasidagi masofa 1,95-2,4sm o'rtacha $2,1 \pm 0,065$ sm tashkil qiladi. Ok kalamushning jigarining kalinaligi 2,8-3,5sm o'rtachasi $3,15 \pm 0,1$ sm ga teng.

Rasm 1. Oq zotsiz kalamush jigar to'qimasi. Bo'laklararo vena to'laqonli holatda(1), sinusoidal bo'shliqlar kengaygan holatda(2), yadrolari lizisga uchragan gepatotsitlar(3), normal saqlangan gepatotsitlar(4), kupfer hujayralar migratsiyasi (5). Bo'yoq: gematoksilin-eozin.

Gepatotsitlarning ko'ndalang o'lchami 21,0 dan 28,0 mkm gacha, o'rtacha - $22,6 \pm 0,7$ mkm gacha o'zgaradi. Ular aniq chegaralar bilan ko'pburchak shaklga ega. Gepatotsitlar sitoplazmasining

o'rtacha ko'ndalang maydonning ko'rsatkichlari 480,0 mkm dan 720,0 mkm gacha, o'rtacha - $644,4 \pm 19,97$ mkm gacha bo'ladi. 100 ta gepatotsitlarga binuklear gepatotsitlarning soni 10-18 oralig'ida bo'lib, o'rtacha $12,6 \pm 0,39$ ga teng. Kalamushlarning nazorat guruhi gepatotsit yadrolarining ko'ndalang kesimi ko'rsatkichlari 78 mkm dan 106 mkm gacha, o'rtacha - $80,06 \pm 2,53$ mkm gacha.

Jigar bo'laklarining markazida jigar tomirlarining dastlabki aloqasi bo'lgan markaziy tomirlar mavjud. Markaziy venalarning diametri 42,0 dan 65,0 mkm gacha, o'rtacha - $52,02 \pm 1,6$ mkm gacha. Portal traktlari arteriya, vena va o't yo'lini o'z ichiga olgan bo'laklar atrofiga joylashgan.

Bo'laklararo venalar diametri 20,0 dan 31,0 mkm gacha, o'rtacha - $26,2 \pm 0,81$ mkm gacha.

Bo'laklararo arteriyalarning diametri 8 dan 15 mkm gacha, o'rtacha $12,64 \pm 0,39$ mkm gacha bo'ladi.

Sinusoidal kapillyarlar asosan radial yo'nalishda bo'laklarning markaziga yo'naltiriladi, ular markaziy tomirlarga oqib o'tadi. Bu gemokapillyarlar ko'ndalang kesimda 9,0 dan 13,0 mkm gacha kattalikka ega, o'rtacha - $11 \pm 0,34$ mkm gacha. Gepatotsitning bir tomoni sinusoidga (sinusoid tomonga), boshqa tomoni esa safro kapillyarlari (safro tomonga) hosil bo'lgan qo'shni gepatotsitga duch keladi.

Rasm 2 Oq zotsiz kalamush jigar to'qimasi. Bo'laklararo vena to'laqonli holatda(1), sinusoidal bo'shliqlar kengaygan holatda(2), yadrolari lizisga uchragan gepatotsitlar(3), Kupfer hujayra migratsiyasi (4). Bo'yoq: gematoksilin-eozin.

Triadaning o't yo'llari bir qavatli kubsimon epiteliy bilan qoplangan bo'lib, balandligi 4 dan 6 mkm gacha, o'rtacha $4,77 \pm 0,14$ mkm gacha bo'ladi. O't yo'llarining kattaligi 14,0 dan 28 mkm gacha, o'rtacha - $19,5 \pm 0,60$ mkm. Portal traktlar va markaziy tomirlar orasidagi parenxima ikki qator jigar hujayralaridan iborat bo'lakchalar bilan ifodalanadi.

Xotima. Tadqiqotning beshinchi bosqichida besh turdagi dorilardan foydalanilganda shu guruhga mansub oq zotsiz kalamush jigari morfologik (gistologik) ko'rinishi o'rganilganda, jigar to'qimasi, markaziy venada notekis to'laqonlik, sentrolobulyar gepatotsitlarda monotsellyulyar nekroz (42.1%, n=6), gepatotsitlarda sust shakllangan tomchili yog'li distrofiya o'choqlari (32.4%, n=5) aniqlandi. Olingan natijalardan ko'rinib turibdiki, oq zotsiz kalamushlar jigaridagi salbiy morfologik o'zgarishlar uchrash intensivligi 5-guruhda 4-guruhga nisbatan ko'p bo'ldi.

Beshinchi guruhga mansub oq zotsiz kalamushlar jigari morfologik xususiyatlaridan quyidagi o'zgarishlar uchrash intensivligi ko'payganini ko'rsatish mumkin: gepatotsitlar guruhi lizisga

uchragan, sinusoidal bo'shliqlar to'laqonligi (70,0%, n=10), aksariyat gepatotsitlar yadrosi giperxromli (70,0%, n=10), shuningdek, sinusoidal bo'shliqlar gepatotsitlar atrofida bir xil kenglikda (56.6%, n=8) bo'lib, gepatotsitlarda nekrozga uchragan sohada sinusoidal bo'shliqlar kengayishi va to'laqonli bo'lishi (50.2%, n=6) kuzatilgan.

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Статья поступила в редакцию 11.07.2024; одобрена после рецензирования 21.08.2024; принята к публикации 24.08.2024.

The article was submitted 11.07.2024; approved after reviewing 21.08.2024; accepted for publication 24.08.2024.

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Источники финансирования: Работа не имела специального финансирования.

Конфликт интересов: Авторы декларируют отсутствие явных и потенциальных конфликтов интересов, связанных с публикацией настоящей статьи.

Вклад авторов:

Усанов С.С. — идеологическая концепция работы, написание текста; редактирование статьи; Абдураимов З.А. — сбор и анализ источников литературы, написание текста.

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Sources of funding: The work did not receive any specific funding.

Conflict of interest: The authors declare no explicit or potential conflicts of interest associated with the publication of this article.

Contribution of the authors:

Usanov S.S. — the ideological concept of the work, writing the text; editing the article;

Abduraimov Z.A. — collection and analysis of literature sources, writing a text.

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ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

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JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 4

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